

1. Vision short name	2. Resistance from the status quo	3. Comprehensiveness	4. Specific nature value orientation	5. Real world example
<p>Provide a short name for the vision.</p>	<p>Through joint discussion, holistically assess how likely the implementation of the vision is to encounter resistance from the status quo, i.e., powerful actors in the relevant (sub-)system opposing transformative change. For this, use the document Integrated simplified Content Analysis Coding Sheet Visions June30th and complement it with coders' scores <i>Plausible, Tangible, Relevant</i>, and <i>Motivational</i> found in document IPBES TCA Chapter 2 Most Transformative Visions Descriptions 19 June 2023 (1).</p> <p>2A -> Assign a score from 0 (low resistance) to 10 (high resistance). 2B -> Justify the score.</p>	<p>Through joint discussion, and based on the document Integrated simplified Content Analysis Coding Sheet Visions June30th, holistically assess the extent to which the vision targets both sustainability and equity; it addresses indirect drivers; it entails a change in views (what we think and feel), actions (what we do), structures and institutions (the things that influence how we think, feel and act); and it rearranges power relations. More detailed definitions of these terms can be found in document Full Assessment Sheet for Most Potentially Transformative Visions update.</p> <p>3A -> Assign a score from 0 (un-dimensional) to 10 (comprehensive). 3B -> Justify the score.</p>	<p>Through joint discussion, assign the vision to one of the seven areas of the NFF triangle: 1) almost exclusively relational; 2) almost exclusively intrinsic; 3) almost exclusively instrumental; 4) between relational and intrinsic without instrumental component; 5) between intrinsic and instrumental without relational component; 6) between relational and instrumental without intrinsic component; 7) balance between relational, intrinsic, and instrumental. Definitions of value types can be found in document Content Analysis Coding Framework with definitions.</p> <p>4A -> Assign one area number. 4B -> Justify the area number.</p> <div data-bbox="1285 810 1675 1072" data-label="Diagram"> </div>	<p>If you know of any example where this vision has inspired transformative change, please explain where, how, by whom, positive/negative effects, etc. Focus on resistance and comprehensiveness with the audience of policymakers in mind. Provide a link. This can be completed with information from the case study database or personal knowledge.</p>

1. Vision name + ID database + no. figure 2.5	2. Resistance		3. Comprehensiveness		4. Specific nature value orientation		5. Real world example
	2A	2B	3A	3B	4A	4B	
Circular Economics 15, 28, 29, 33, 34, 38, 46, 47, 48, 60, 63, 65, 70 1	3	Uses language, ideas familiar to business, maintains growth orientation or at least does not directly question it, emphasizes production processes. Economic orientation. Circularity language is naturally appealing. Opportunities (new jobs, new inputs) stemming from the changes proposed, are also appealing to businesses.	4	Focus is mainly changing productive processes, entails some changes in views (particularly within businesses) and actions. Productive structures and associated societal changes would accompany CE. Maintains or does not challenge growth orientation. However desired growth is not purely GDP growth but growth in stocks (including natural, human, cultural and manufactured stocks). And changes in economic system design/implementation intended to leave more space to nature.	3	While there is a hint of intrinsic natural value, the predominant orientation is NS.	MacArthur Foundation reports give a lot of examples (local or sector-based) where circular approaches are being tried.
Degrowth and Steady State 23, 61, 62, 64, 65, 67, 68, 73 2	7	'Down'-scale of change for businesses and economic systems is huge, with population also coming under control, both of which would likely be resisted by incumbent power holders and the majority of population that associates degrowth with recession. That said, there is a quite powerful movement behind these ideas, pushing them forward which might enhance feasibility. Degrowth has become increasingly influential in sustainability debate. Steady-state is one of the 'sources' of vision 'Wellbeing for all'.	8	Significant changes in views, values (sufficiency instead of efficiency, etc.), actions and systemic structures implied, including productive and social practices. Targets equity and sustainability. Focus is not only on economic production but on alternative ways of consuming and organizing collective life, strong focus on conviviality and democracy. Implications for all indirect drivers. Focus on democracy would rearrange power relations.	4-7	This vision is meant to move away from the solely instrumental (exploitative) use of nature, though its use is still present. Intrinsic is possibly most evident, followed by relational and instrumental values in some degree of balance. Instrumental components low in degrowth, perhaps a bit more important in steady-state.	Seems to be mainly present in the academic literature to date, with few places or industries implementing. We have several examples of downshiffters or degrowth-inspired activists implementing these ideas in the form of consumption cooperatives, urban gardening, repair workshops, etc. Degrowth policy proposals like work time reduction have been implemented in several countries as part of progressive mainstream measures.
Economics of Biodiversity 16 3	5	Couched in regenerative economics language, recognition of nature in new ways, transparency, requires significant governance, narrative, and behavioral shifts	6	Significant changes in views, values (human embeddedness in nature), along with recognition of human ingenuity, participatory processes, and moving beyond materialism—view, values, actions, structures all	7-3	A combination and seeming relatively equal balance of intrinsic, instrumental, and relational values deeply embedded in this vision, which would be highly transformative if achieved.	Comes from an economist, and has considerable visibility, but other than being likely to already being practiced by some IPs, and in line with circular economics, wellbeing economics, doughnut economics,

		that will be hard to achieve. Some aspects will appeal to many people (motivational) if properly framed. Strict economic framing may convince orthodox economists more than other less economistic visions.		implicated. Emphasis on sustainability. Some emphasis on equity. Addresses all indirect drivers. Power shifts are not clear.			but too new a publication to be implemented as yet—and needs to be taken up by policymakers seriously.
Wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries 1, 21, 27, 54, 30, 31, 36, 59, 66, 71, 72, 74 4	4	Couched in familiar, friendly economic terminology along with planetary limits language. Has feasibility, tangibility, relevance, qualities, could potentially be motivational beyond radical social movements. Clear relevance in the context of climate change and other issues, emphasizes social equity and strong values that will appeal to many if promulgated. Of course, there are barriers in the form of extant power holders/structures.	8	Highly potentially transformative. Addresses sustainability and equity. Deals with all indirect drivers. Affecting all dimensions of views and values, actions, structures, and institutions, which would change to come into new alignments around wellbeing (for all) within planetary boundaries, goals likely to be appealing to many, despite likely redistribution of resources and wealth (if implemented), and significant shifts in actions/structures. Growth 'agnosticism' (at least re doughnut) means exploitation may continue, though a shift towards regenerativity is implied. Perhaps not a big emphasis in power shifts.	7	All three sets of values are implied in this vision in a good balance: <i>Instrumental</i> : reduced (though continuing) use of environmental resources and shifts away from exploitative practices, <i>Intrinsic</i> : resource sanctuaries and limits to large infrastructures, value of understanding limits—planetary boundaries, <i>Relational</i> : stewardship, localism, and relationality all emphasized. (NOTE: I think it is important to recognize instrumental values, too, here).	Some of these approaches, e.g., wellbeing economics and doughnut are being adopted and put in place, e.g., in Amsterdam (doughnut), and Scotland, New Zealand, Wales, some cities in California and Canada. We can write a box with a combination of these examples at different scales showing potential and limitation of this vision in triggering TC. Alternatively, to the box, a short text could go in section (2-3 sentences).
Natural Social Contract 69 5	5	Describes a highly motivational fairer, more ecologically-conscious society based on a natural social contract and similar ideas to wellbeing for all above, so there is some feasibility, albeit significant change is needed to get to collaborative/deliberative governance, needed shifts in values, and equity. There are tangible aspects, and the vision is holistic, but moving towards it would be difficult in the status quo because of existing	7	Multi-dimensional, strongly emphasizes equity and flourishing for all, polycentric/distributed forms of governance, and sustainability. Would impact views and values strongly and consequent actions and governance (structural and institutional) changes would be significant. No information about direct drivers.	1-6	Strongly relational values based on social-ecological systems and interconnectedness perspectives, while relying on natural resources for continued productive activities. Written in 'human'/'humane' terms rather than business terms, so instrumental orientation is less, though present, and intrinsic values appear to be generally missing. Not enough information to classify this one. Normally when one speaks about a greater ecosystem to which we belong, this indicates intrinsic component. But it would be a big	Unsure. The paper is relatively new, and probably it is too soon for implementation or social movements around this idea to be in place.

		power and governance structures. Resorting to the natural state of human beings (group life and part of a bigger ecosystem), speaks to human's need to feel part of something bigger and 'naturalizes' change.				assumption and we don't consider it.	
Ecocivilization 352 6	6	Motivational for the ecology (biodiversity) community, probably less so for others less familiar. Relational /connectedness qualities have spiritual overtones, and common/shared understandings could be motivating and relevant to some. There are tangible aspects, but overall plausibility is relatively weak, though adoption of 'integrated' and harmony w/ nature perspectives are clear. Power shifts ('women-led') likely to meet resistance.	6	Emphasizes restoration/focus on biodiversity, justice, balancing humans in nature, new connectivity, collaboration and cooperation, particularly around governance via networks. Requires significant shift of views (paradigms) and understanding, along with values and actions. Power structures (governance) would also dramatically shift. Indirect drivers like economic or demographic factors are not addressed.	4	Highly relational as 'essence of society is relationships'. Cooperative. Also, strong intrinsic valuing of nature. Both values come through strongly. Instrumental is absent.	There may be small communities or Indigenous communities where these values and cooperative spirit, plus, harmony with nature, are at play. Note: China and David Korten argue also for 'ecological civilization', framed in different ways, without quite as central a biodiversity focus.
Future Ukraine 232, 1047, 1048 7	6	Highly ecosystem-friendly, but economically-driven visions, therefore (if the war ends), some plausibility, tangibility, and appeal to business, using an integrated landscape management approach (plausible, lending to feasibility) and emphasizing nature-based solutions, ecologically conscious consumption, collaboration among institutions and ecosystem services.	4	Relatively realistic economic orientation, many social factors not considered, so more nature- than people-oriented, thus not totally holistic. Targets only some indirect drivers. Does require significant shifts in views and values (eco-friendly policies), shifts in land, sea, ecosystem uses (actions) and treatment (structural shifts). It is rather an anthropocentric perspective.	3	Highly economically oriented, therefore mostly instrumental, with some slight (much less) emphasis on both intrinsic and relational values.	No, with the ongoing war, ecosystems are being destroyed and Ukraine is most likely not implementing this vision.
Steps for Change 85	7	Dance piece to create awareness of the planet's plight of biodiversity loss and	5	The actual dance piece embodies a strong change in views. As for actions, nature restoration is proposed and	4	Place directly between intrinsic and relational (no instrumental values seem present).	Dance piece. There is nothing to implement.

8		urgent need for "a step change". No pathways, or change strategies seem to be articulated, hence while there appears to be a degree of tangibility, clearly some relevance to the particular audience and a motivational element to the piece, the plausibility and overall feasibility seems limited (a judgment call).		considered to have the potential to reach thriving ecosystems for nature and people. Relevant to specific types of ecosystems. Little information is present about how actions, and institutional structures would need to change to achieve the outcome, thus overall scope and multi-dimensionality are limited. Equity not addressed but strong on sustainability. Indirect drivers not addressed.			
Latin American Agroecological Society 830 9	4	Promoting agroecology, good living (buen vivir) across multiple countries in Latin America, seems like a tangible, reasonably plausible, relevant, and potentially motivational approach for the region.	7	Covers multiple areas of socio-ecologies, biodiversity, living well for people, holistic health and ecosystem health, conservation and the like. Addresses sustainability and equity. Views and values that support these things seem to potentially already be present, though needing further support, actions are identified and potentially supported, ILK is included. Would imply significant land, natural resource use shifts in structures/practices as well as power shifts. Addresses several indirect drivers but not demographic.	1	Predominantly relational.	Perhaps so, as there appear to be many documents and support from FAO. Gervasio could provide some examples. Agroecology is a 'discrete' approach yet very transformative that speaks to the needs of millions of small farmers around the world. Potential box.
Food and Agriculture Organization 834 10	3	Food/agricultural shifts, oriented to ending hunger, uses SDGs as reference point and framing device. Relatively narrow focus (though food production and equity have many systemic aspects, including productivity, security, inclusiveness, equity). Goals seem tangible, plausible, relevant, albeit approach does not seem motivational.	5	Focus emphasizes food production, security, equity, covers sea and land, including sustainable agriculture. From what is written, it does not seem to cover much socio-economic territory, where changes need to take place. However, it addresses some indirect drivers and changes in structures. Except for SDGs, no real discussion of shifts in views and values, actions to be taken or structural changes seem to be relatively narrowly defined. There are several actions that FAO does as well	6-3	It seems mostly instrumental, related to agricultural productivity and food security. Some relational values are included. However, the orientation is mostly instrumental, with just a touch of relational and perhaps much less intrinsic.	There are likely many examples on the website.

				as change in structures including land reform.			
Agricultural and Rural Prospective Initiative 879 11	4	The general feasibility of 'creating a space for reflection, dialogue and proposals' related to agriculture/rural policies in Senegal and West Africa is highly feasible, however, it is not particularly motivational and relevance, tangibility would be questionable. I.e., feasible but not likely to make much of a difference, very much business as usual.	3	Seems pretty much in line with conventional economic thinking, business as usual, with (e.g.) climate change mitigation, supporting existing institutions fostering a sustainability (not transformation) agenda, except in very local cases. Supporting peasant orgs, mostly analysis oriented in ways that try to shift public policies. No evidence of changing views and values, actions (except in incremental ways), structures and institutions. It is a liberal economic transformative change, for example they want economic liberalization and agrarian reform. They address some indirect drivers. Social equity included.	3	From what is present, seems fully instrumental orientation, based in conventional economic thinking.	Yes, it appears there may be information on some policies that have been implemented, though as noted seems pretty much in line with conventional economic thinking.
Agroecological Resources Space 887 12	4	Highly locally tangible work, emphasizing agroecology, specific populations and crop diversity. Seems plausible and quite feasible within its focus arena, presumably motivational to its target audience.	7	Local focus on peasant women, small gardeners, etc., advancing social recognition, food sovereignty, fair consumption/production. Agroecology, equity, localism. Targets some indirect drivers. Considerable shift in views and values, not focus on structures.	4	Highly relational (cultural heritage, balance w/ nature) (agroecology), with minor aspects of intrinsic values.	Probably some of the projects undertaken would provide insight into application. Could be part of a box on implementation of or inspiration by agroecology visions together with the other agroecological visions.
World Farmers Organization 893 13	3	Advocacy/voice for farmers, farmer-driven approach. Specific community, emphasis on best practice, practical solutions, including technological solutions: seems highly feasible, tangible, presumably motivational for farmers, albeit limited scope of impact.	5	Sector focus on farmers and agricultural cooperators, 'voice' oriented, includes focus on sustainable agriculture and use of ecosystems. Specific attention to farmers' views and values (re ecosystems and farming practices), actions, and local 'voice', plus (local) structures and institution seems present. Scope is limited to farming livelihoods and practices, so not very broad or multi-dimensional. Addresses only 1 indirect driver. Not emphasizing	3	From description seems almost fully instrumental, e.g., 'use of ecosystems', sustainable agricultural, rural livelihoods orientation, though some relational (social) components exist (e.g., among farmers).	Yes, implementation seems to be under way in some locations.

				equity. Strong in power shifts (farmers' voice).			
The Ministry for the Future 162 14	6	Fictional account, much dystopia, advocacy for a 'ministry for the future' that would handle ecological (climate change, other losses) issues. Requires crisis to get there, many obstacles and human-nature crises. Feasibility, realism builds on pathways that seem plausible, tangibility is not clear, and motivational quality also not clear, albeit there is significant relevance to how things are today. Motivated stakeholders are also a force of change besides crisis.	5	Crisis shifts human views and values (at least partially, though nature is still viewed as needing to support human existence/prosperity). The idea of a ministry would require significant structural and institutional change, with attendant changes in practices. Establishment of ministry entails and derives from change in views, structures and actions, sustainability and equity (refugees) are fully addressed, but not clear how indirect drivers and power are addressed.	3-5	Largely instrumental orientation. Nature supporting human life. The creation of a Ministry to defend all living creatures who cannot speak for themselves is an intrinsic value orientation.	Book is fiction and somewhat dystopian (my own reading), though offering hope at the end. No implementation.
Princess Mononoke 166 15	6	Fictional account, clash of civilizations—human and nature worlds, consequences (somewhat dystopian sounding), need to overcome forces of industrialization. Does not seem feasible (clash is plausible and lacks tangibility as described) but not in positive ways, could be inspirational/motivational for reform purposes, relevance is somewhat questionable.	5	Views and values would shift significantly to bring stewardship of whole system into existence, equity and justice, too. Would significantly shift power, institutions and structures if achieved, giving value to nature, yet changes in structures and institutions are not described. Sustainability and equity addressed. Does not seem to address indirect drivers.	1	Highly relational, orientation towards humans living in harmony with nature, overcoming processes of industrialization (instrumental).	Fictional account, no implementation.
Buen Vivir 588 16	4	Focus on 'radical ruralities', different from capitalist logic, based in ILK and good living ideas. Being implemented w/ significant tensions emerging and shifts as the concept develops, moving away from capitalism, therefore has some feasibility, tangibility (tensions	7	Development narrative shifts local contexts away from capitalistic motivations towards 'good living' (wellbeing, buen vivir). Requires significant shifts in views and values (inclusiveness, harmony w/ nature), and recognition of relationality (connectedness). Also requires shifts in consequent actions—with	1-4	Highly relational, biocentric and collective perspective. Emphasis on buen vivir (good living). Biocentric perspectives are often linked to intrinsic values.	Being implemented in some places. Significant tensions arising noted in description.

		emerging, require ongoing shifts in practice), motivational (inspiring vision), and quite relevant.		implications for power, structure, and institutions. Quite holistic at various local scales. Equity and sustainability addressed. It addresses only a few indirect drivers.			
Resilience Lab 739 17	3	Local scale, shifting relationships to urban areas, sustainability issues therein, at the neighborhood level, with significant tangibility, plausibility, and overall feasibility potential, through narrative change—that would ultimately shift behaviors and practices. High degree of potential relevance to locals, and potentially quite motivating.	5	Emphasis is on urban places, sustainability, community relationships, social cohesion. New narratives suggest significant changes in paradigms or views and local values, as well as shifting relationships therefore new types of actions, with implications for relationship to place (power?), structures, and maybe institutions though that is not clear. Scale is limited, though there could be propagational impacts elsewhere. Indirect drivers not sufficiently addressed. Structures not addressed concretely. Upscaling/propagational potential is there. Local not necessarily less transformative.	1	Highly relational, oriented to place, strengthening of people/neighborhood (nature?) relationships, community relationships.	Probably the paper has an example of implementation.
Rhiz(h)ome 741 18	5	Equitable governance, participation, reduced racism in Southern Africa implied, citizen-led governance, inclusiveness. Motivational quality is high, plausibility considerably less so in current context (power holders would resist), tangibility seems high, and relevance is clear.	7	Scope is Southern Africa, interconnected green cities. Strong people orientation (strong in equity and inclusion of marginalized groups), though significant views and values changes implied (end obsession w/ material goods), business purpose shifts, implying significant power, structural and institutional shifts. Broad set of value shifts indicated. Radical change in concept of work, away from alienation. Main indirect drivers addressed except demographic factors.	1-4-7	Instrumental orientation (earth as collective resource) although suggested shifts away from output-based economy suggest a move away from instrumentalism. Some intrinsic present—nature as source of inspiration, core to how cities work. The notion of stewardship speaks centrally to relational values.	We don't know of examples; we assume it is not being implemented yet.
Radical TransLocal 744 19	5	Technological 'fix' (machine learning system, full eco-costing), not currently particularly plausible, nor are the governance or economic	8	Techno-fix, sharing/gift economy, community-driven governance, connection to Mother Earth, local decision making. All imply significant shifts in views and values, highly	4	Highly relational—community-driven decisions, ILK based, connected to Earth, learning oriented. Eco-centrism is (like bio-centrism) related to intrinsic values.	We don't know of examples; we assume it is not being implemented yet.

		shifts indicated, though there is considerable tangibility to the vision, relevance and inspirational quality seem limited.		holistic except for techno-fix orientation, otherwise significant shifts in power relations (direct democracy), structures and institutions are implicated (no nation states for example). It addresses both sustainability and (intergenerational) equity. Addresses all indirect drivers (regarding demography it is one of the few visions that speaks about reduced forced migrations). It is not a simple techno-fix, although technology facilitates the balanced relation with the Earth. 'Going back to the roots of humanity' speaks about a much deeper change. All decisions are bound by a deep commitment to the protection and health of the environment. There is an understanding that the Earth nurtures, heals, provides and supports.		Vision should fall between relational and intrinsic.	
Twitter on circular economy 904 20	3	'Assumes' economic, tech, env't transformation. Emphasis on circular economies, which is plausible and tangible, potentially motivational to business interests (and technologists). Plausibility is reasonably high, there is some degree of relevance, though significant changes are not really implied beyond circularity of production processes.	4	Assumption of transformation embedded, focus on water, plus restorative, regenerative systems (circularity, collaboration and systemic resilience). Growth orientation is embedded in CE so while CE is a shift in views and to some extent values, not as dramatic as other possibilities (though important), actions associated with implementation of businesses would shift significantly, while power structures and institutions remain much the same. Addresses sustainability but does not address equity. Not so much focus on indirect drivers.	3	Instrumental orientation, circular economy emphasis.	No indication of implication in write-up.
Ukraine Recovery Vision	5	Despite the devastation of the ongoing war, this plan seems to outline a significant, plausible,	5	Generally holistic vision that includes many aspects of nature and society, including integration of humans and	3-5	Instrumental, focuses mainly on economic recovery, competition, economic and other infrastructure,	War is ongoing at this writing, so no implementation as yet, though understanding is that they plan to

227, 229 21		highly tangible, relevant, and motivational pathway forward. The issue is that the country will be (is) completely devastated and getting to these goals will be very difficult, reducing overall feasibility.			nature, equity, and justice. Implications (post-war recovery) for structural, institutional, and power relations changes are significant, although it is not entirely clear how much views and values would change from their current ones. Actions to respond to war devastation are significant. Addresses several indirect drivers.	with some relational implications for recovery around rebuilding in eco-friendly and respectful ways that preserve natural resources. Little sense of intrinsic value of nature, except for the goal to restore wildlife and network of centers for rescue of wild animals.	implement some aspects of it even before a complete peace agreement.
Os Miñarzos Marine Reserve 409 22	4	Since it appears to have achieved significant transformative impact within the local context, there is a good degree of plausibility, tangibility, relevance and apparent motivation to engage in these processes in this community. The MPA has been already implemented.	9	6	Marine protected area for management approach, democratic innovation. Locally transformative of views and values, actions have been taken, including conflict reduction, and seeming reorganizing of the institutions, power relations, and structures associated with small scale fisheries. The system has been already reorganized, with a decentralized and democratic way to take decisions. Trust and cooperation are key elements of the co-management system. Targeting both sustainability and equity questions. Addresses some indirect drivers, e.g., the creation of the MPA is allowing to mitigate out-migration of people from the coast by establishing local population.	Both instrumental (improve fishing resources) and relational (new human-ocean relationships, plus new local governance and voice relations).	Yes, seems to be a case of some degree of transformation within this limited context. Can put this vision in a box. Be careful of this as we already include it in section 2.2. about visioning process (Saul suggested to include it) (Avoid repetition). A case study of TC has been included in database, we could make link to vision in text or box. The MPA has inspired other neighboring communities to propose another MPA of fishing interest on the Northern coast of Galicia (Decree 28/2009, of January 29, creating the Marine Reserve of Fishing Interest Ría de Cedeira), while a procedure for the extension of the MPA of Os Miñarzos has also been initiated and it is currently in the final stage. The case of Os Miñarzos also inspired other coastal communities not only in other regions of Spain (namely Catalonia and Andalucía), but also the new fisheries Law in Portugal as well as the Voluntary Guidelines for Securing Sustainable Small-scale Fisheries in the Context of Food Security and Poverty Eradication developed by FAO. All of these

							initiatives inspired by the Os Miñarzos case have been highly positive to develop new sustainable trajectories, and they are currently in different phases of development and degree of success. More recently, the transformative initiative initiated in Os Miñarzos served as the seed to create a new network of small-scale fishers in Latin America and the Caribbean, Portugal and Spain, involving more than 20 million of fishers (women).
Closing high seas to fishing 359 23	6	Global fisheries catch would not be reduced, improves plausibility, feasibility overall of this vision. Very relevant to fishers and the fishing industry, it could potentially be quite motivational beyond the immediate context if understanding broadly shared. Closing the high sea would help to change the practice as these vessels will need to be removed from the oceans, as their activities are affecting not only marine biodiversity but also impacting on coastal resources as they compete with small-scale vessels too. Industry and society would internalize the importance of caring for marine biodiversity and use public money to protect biodiversity instead of destroying it.	8	Changes in views and values regarding parts of the ocean needed (no catch), with actions to close some areas to fishers. Structural, institutional, and power changes are implied with different forms of governance, though scope is limited to the high seas. Closing the high sea would be highly beneficial (indirectly) to the developing world as these fleets who operate in the high sea are heavily subsidized and also operate in the exclusive economic zones of developing countries, putting at risk their food security. Thus, equity and justice considerations are taken into account alongside sustainability. Addresses crucial economic and governance drivers (subsidies, etc.) of unsustainable fishing.	3	Instrumental: use of seas for fishing, increasing/not decreasing catch.	Seems to be a study oriented towards influencing high seas policy. Not implemented yet, but highly inspirational and powerful.
Ocean Climate Resilience 364	7	Internalizing shadow prices for harvested fish (blue carbon content), provides alternatives. Whether policymakers would	6	Limited in scope to fisheries, with some shifts implied (structures, e.g., internalization of costs), but reconsidering the importance of small-	3-(6)	Instrumental, reflects economic activity and efficiency, including equitable income distribution arising from marine resources.	A study of the 'yearly willingness to sequester carbon' re the fishing industry.

24		go along potentially reduces feasibility, but the general scheme appears plausible, is highly tangible, uses market-based solutions, and is in line with climate goals. Not sure how motivational this plan is, but it is highly relevant, and potentially impactful. The plan is feasible technically speaking but need to recognize that for some countries (e.g. rich nations such Japan, the EU) maybe can be difficult to implement due to pressures from industry. Not implemented yet, potential barriers from the industry to operationalize at national levels by countries.		scale fishers implies a change of views of policy makers. Large reduction of extraction activities is in itself a shifted view if we compare with current extractivist logic. Actions are also considered, if the fisheries sector is included in the market scheme, society would have a practical tool to include the importance of the value of carbon from the ocean. On the whole power structures and institutions would be mostly the same, with different guidelines of practice. The power asymmetries between large industries and small fishers would radically change by implementing these mechanisms. Deals with equity and sustainability. Addresses some indirect drivers but attempts to fix sustainability problem with market-based mechanism, thus with status-quo method (which can however lead to transformative changes).		Highly instrumental. However, the way to give more importance to small-scale fisheries will help to improve relational (although with less importance than instrumental) values with coastal communities.	
Blue Transformation 366 25	3	Seems highly tangible and plausible as existing knowledge is used for innovations that largely do not appear to disturb the status quo. Not particularly motivational (inspiring), yet highly relevant as actors can readily adopt some of these changes without other significant changes. The scope is sectoral but huge! It includes fisheries, aquaculture and value chains, therefore, really huge.	5	Uses existing knowledge, tools to continue aquatic food system supply (not transformative), though promotes innovations (incremental, most likely) though complexity is considered, as well as multi-stakeholder input. Incremental approaches imply few changes in any of the factors associated with transformation, rather innovations. Scope and impact are limited.	3	Highly instrumental, no suggestion of the other values implied.	
Ark of the seas 368 26	2	Localism, use of local resources is tangible, plausible, relevant	6	The views and power structures are changing, removing previous asymmetries between large-small producers, therefore, there is a	3-6	Although highly instrumental, the way the initiative values local and sustainable species and producers, it also implicitly values the	It is already implemented at the local level, plan to develop it in other (big) countries (e.g China). .

		(not sure how motivational). Steps being taken are incremental not transformative, though localism is evident. It is a local initiative already implemented and developed by the largest textile company in the world. Indeed, they are already implementing the same method in the rest of Spain and in 2024 and 2025 they will start in Asia (India, China, etc.) too. The initiative gained a lot of traction both between the local producers, the company and other actors (media, government).		change in the values (more importance to small and local producers), and helped to reduce/remove intermediaries by linking the company directly to producers/consumers. Healthier food at lower prices. Change in views is present in the wish to source food locally and sustainably. Addresses equity and sustainability. Addresses direct drivers but fewer indirect drivers. Risk of greenwashing as implemented in largest textile company in the world.		relational value between land/ocean and people.	Strength is that it is not only a vision but also an ongoing project.
One with the Tao 908 27	5	Taoist philosophy of one with all. Not a lot of details were provided to suggest how plausible (though this philosophy has been around for millennia), tangibility is somewhat limited, could be motivational though major shift of views and required for many to get concrete steps in place. For someone that starts meditating or being interested in spirituality, it is indeed difficult to operationalize. However, the book is probably one of the most translated and read books of humanity, this speaks to the motivational aspect. One of the few classic spiritual visions that speaks directly to those in charge of public affairs.	7	If adopted, significant implications for oneness, 'letting be' what is, humility, and other values. Crucial insight of spontaneous self-transformation. Would require significant shifts in views and values if implemented on a broad scale (with consequent shifts in power structures, actions, and, presumably institutions). One of the few spiritual visions that speaks about equity. Indirect drivers are not very much addressed. Lack of specifics re biodiversity and current structures. Inner component of the vision is essential to transform other spheres (practices, structures, etc.) (Monica Sharma book, Riane Eisler's work on partnership cultures)	4 (closer to 1)	Contemplation of Tao and awakening of Tao within as well as being one with the world sits well within relational but we could also assume within intrinsic – it is a praise of the Tao's immense goodness. Tao is not nature but the Mother of nature and the cosmos, but this argument should be ok.	Ecological civilization vision builds on Taoist ideas, as well as the paper by Ma et al where they advocate for a more integrated vision of unity between humans and nature for the 2050 vision.

<p>The garden of paradise 911</p> <p>28</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>Quran, values, here symbolic eternal values, but few concrete elements to indicate plausibility, tangibility, relevance, though clearly some people are highly motivated by this text.</p>	<p>6</p> <p>Significant implications for views and values (inner transformation), however lacks specifics on biodiversity and current structures and relies on a divinity rather than human intervention. Relationship to power structures (except from divinity, which implies continued centralized control), specific actions, and institutions not really mentioned. Indirect drivers and equity not addressed. Complete abundance, satisfaction and joy, state of everlasting bliss and harmony with cosmos. It speaks about inner transformation (like Tao vision).</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Relational, does emphasize quality of life somewhat. Nature is used symbolically to describe a state of paradise where God delivers joy to people. Nature thus mediates (symbolically) the relation between God and people. The garden and fountains (nature) give food and drink, but it is not in the sense of a material ecosystem service.</p>	<p>Similarly to Tao, examples can be given of Muslim-led cases of visions which are based on Quran (not in this specific part though, but more in general). This can go in the text (1-2 sentence) would not do a box on this.</p>
<p>Forests of Kalpataru trees 914</p> <p>29</p>	<p>6</p>	<p>The tree metaphor is potentially powerful (motivational), and the idea of transforming wickedness might appeal to some. Overall lacks tangibility, plausibility, and relevance. Lacks sufficient detail.</p>	<p>6</p> <p>Significant shifts in views and values implied (good deeds, friendliness of all beings—humans in harmony w/ nature). No reference to biodiversity. Presumably actions and other elements of transformation would follow but not specifically discussed, but since details are lacking... It is a short poem, facing common challenges with artistic expressions.</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Here nature (forests of Kalpataru trees, ocean) is used to symbolize the qualities of saints that distribute blessings to normal people. Nature is a symbol that mediates the relation between saints and people. No instrumentality.</p>	
<p>Self-realization saves humans and nature 923</p> <p>30</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Self-realization is the common message of religions. It is based on the awakening of the Kundalini energy. It could be personally transformative, no clear socio-ecological implications, therefore possibly not plausible, motivational. Millions of people in the world have received self-realization following this method. Vision offers a way to actualize the message of classic spiritual</p>	<p>7</p> <p>Values shift significantly (harmony with self, nature, equality), which would likely mean a shift of views as well. It is not clear how power structures, actions, and institutions would change, therefore transformative potential at the individual level may be high, but systemic is not clear. Effects on structures may be similar to those from Gandhi's movement for independence. The main change in values and views is becoming</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>Relational. It addresses materialism and greed through self-realization. It enhances spiritual and relational quality of life. Some descriptions of Mother Earth's circularity and wisdom indicate intrinsic value. Self-realization, consequent improvements in quality of life and renewed relationships with nature (being part of it) would sit more in relational. The instrumental value of Mother Earth is also recognized (food, shelter, etc.).</p>	<p>It decreases materialism, but indication of broad-based implementation needs to be further substantiated. Radical changes in lifestyles, values, health and personality traits have been reported by research. Also associated with more sustainable decision-making through fisheries game experiment comparing meditators and non-meditators. A case study based on this initiative</p>

		visions which are low in feasibility, and this approach helps make them feasible.		collectively conscious through the activation of the parasympathetic nervous system, which actualizes transformative change. Links to increased Corporate Social Responsibility. It lacks specifics re biodiversity.			has been included in the case study database.
Towards a Global Ethic 924 31	2	Articulation of vision in several principles/directives and clear explanations help people envision the desired future (tangibility). Relevance is assured as it contains calls to action/reflection targeting specific stakeholders. Motivational for both religious and non-religious people. Highly feasible.	8	Addresses nature degradation and has a strong focus on equality. It is clear that unjust economic institutions and structures based on greed need to be transformed, as well as the moral foundations of such structures and the hearts and the consciousness where they lie. Values and views thus clearly shifted (interdependence, responsibility, forgiveness, just social and economic structures, humankind is a family). Several actions mentioned. Important power shifts implied.	1-(4)	Strong relational component with mention of interdependence between the Earth's components (including humans) and the whole. Responsibility also speaks to a relational orientation. Care for life and for the Earth also speaks to relational value although a bit of intrinsic could also be attributed.	This has surely inspired initiatives, but it is difficult to track them. A box or some sentences could be written in the main text grouping all the current religious initiatives and how they are inspired by their visions.
Multi-Faith Response to the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework 931 32	3	Technical, not inspiring (per coder), but derives from a call to action for faith-based organizations, implying narrative shift (for some) w/ respect to nature, which is potentially motivational, is plausible, has a degree of tangibility in its focus, and is highly relevant to the current state of the world.	7	Strong emphasis on reversing biodiversity loss, sacredness of life, sacred wisdom of Indigenous peoples. Clear shift of views and values, associated with many of the world's major religions (put into practice, not just rhetoric). Core values shift to harmony w/ nature, equity, biodiversity preservation, rights of Indigenous peoples. Clear shift of economic priorities and governance institutions and power structures indicated. Potentially transformative if implemented. Rights based approach to conservation.	4	Relational, groups of religious and faith-based organizations. Sacredness of all life (interconnectedness, oneness) It speaks also about intrinsic (something that is sacred has value in itself).	Not clear if being implemented but powerful institutions have signed it and their congregations, followers may be influenced to new actions and understandings Potential box summarizing these initiatives, though challenging to write because there are many and we don't know whether they had impacts on the ground. We could put together Laudato Si, Muslim declaration on climate change, Eco-Sikh, etc.
Global Fishing Watch 1015	4	Rather feasible as it is actually in place. Plausible and clearly relevant for some stakeholders.	6	Addresses sustainability/biodiversity, its purpose includes fairness in ocean use (equity). Only some indirect	3	Instrumental orientation as per coder assessment.	Already being implemented globally. Indigenous people in Centra America already using.

33		Perhaps a bit less motivational if compared to artistic or politically-charged visions. Already in place everywhere (plausible, tangible) and several countries are also using the monitoring data to manage their oceans. The tool is also helping to monitor other economic activities (drugs, human traffic) apart from global fisheries. Improve transparency and use/availability of public data re marine activities.		drivers are addressed, notably technology as it puts big data methods at the service of ocean sustainability. Not sure it entails a huge change in views (beyond sustainable fisheries to which it obviously contributes). Although it can help improve governance, it is not clear how structures and power relations could change. Historically, fishing activities had huge problems in transparency and data reporting (especially rich countries with their distant water fishing vessels). The use of technology to know where vessels operate and provide key information about the position of vessels (governance implications for coastal and transnational fisheries), that helps to know how much fish is extracted from the ocean from big companies (equity dimension)			
Nuru International 961 34	3	Locally (women) led sustainable development, particularly around farming, self-sustaining impact model. Tangibility, plausibility (w/overcoming structural and cultural barriers) seems high, also motivational and locally relevant.	6	Locally-driven farming and agriculture, women-led sometimes, requires shift in views and values, governance structures, therefore actions, power structures, and institutions. Leaves self-sustaining model in place to propagate elsewhere. Targets poverty and equity especially small-scale farmers. Local scale. Not much biodiversity, ecosystem impact. Attention to indirect drivers is low.	3	By inference, purely instrumental values.	Yes, it seems like this approach is actually being implemented in some places.
AI for Good 1012 35	4	Tech solutions, shifts in economic thinking advancing SDGs, multi-sector, disciplinary actions, around AI policy. Could be considered 'tangible' and quite plausible, because fits w/in existing practices and norms w/out much changing,	2	Dataset oriented, empirics driven for tracking and other indicators, dialogue-oriented. Draws from conventional economic and technological approaches. Does not appear transformative, little change in views and values, actions, power	3	Instrumental: accelerating SDG-driven start-ups, sustainable development.	Could be implemented. SDG accelerator may be operational.

		not motivational, relevance questionable.		structures, or institutions. Measurement oriented, not visionary.			
Global Deal for Nature (30 by 30) 300 36	4	Highly visionary, based on Half Earth proposal, therefore potentially motivational, tangible, based in circular and regenerative approaches to economy, w/ multiple specific goals (tangibility), has some plausibility as well, highly relevant in some contexts, though of course achievability is potentially questionable. It is quite powerful and inspirational, potentially more difficult to operationalize.	6	Demanding significant shifts in view and values, actions, as well as power structures and institutions, including the preservation of half the earth for other-than-human species. Protecting both quality of life and nature for its own sake, high transformative potential. Strong focus on biodiversity/sustainability. Equity not addressed. Attention to indirect drivers seems scarce. Possible unintended consequences if implemented (risk of reinforcing historical displacement of Indigenous and Local People from their lands if they are to be 'protected' at large scale). Not so clear how power and structures/institutions will change. Highly contested.	5	Combination of instrumental and intrinsic values that aim at protecting biodiversity and ecosystems as well as enhanced human quality of life.	Unintended implications of this vision could be discussed.
More Sustainable 2030: Living and connecting 690 37	4	Enhanced citizen awareness re healthy oceans, circular economy, eating more seafood, reconnecting communities to oceans (equitable blue economy). Has plausibility, clear tangibility, is very relevant, though not easy to accomplish. Feedback between oceans and human health. Not so motivational, several elements of circular economy are present.	7	Starts w/ changing (world)views and associated values of interactions with nature. Ocean-related views and values, power structures and institutions would all need to shift significantly, with implications for human wellbeing, and the health of oceans (scope is that of oceans). It is unclear how it would help to equity, although decentralization of governance is there. Although it seems relevant, most of the "One health" framework advocate for incremental change rather than transformative ones.	3-(6)	Emphasizes instrumental and relational values that rely on the wellbeing and health of oceans. From the coding, it seems probably more focused on instrumental, though relational is also present.	
Convention on Biological Diversity 127	4	International convention signed by 168 nations, therefore has plausibility, tangibility in its goals (though somewhat general), also highly	7	Goal of humans living in harmony with nature demands significant changes in views and values from the mainstream, along with associated changes in power structures and	5	Intrinsic and instrumental values both important in this vision, though relational values do not seem to appear.	Legally binding treaty, therefore presumably being implemented at least to some extent (however problematically).

38		motivational and very relevant. Challenges related to entering into force, non-binding commitments, etc. Doubts that status quo fully takes up.		institutions implied (governance) (need to develop relevant legislation and regulations, protected areas, reduced exploitation, prevention of invasive species), integrating ILK into mainstream practice. Particularly focused on the preservation and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems, as well as human equity, wellbeing. Indirect drivers of governance, technology, less prominent, technology.			
Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 153 39	3	Many specifics provided, fundamental joint goals of nature, ecosystem, and human wellbeing, including rights of nature, and a holistic ecosystem-based approach. Very ambitious, high-level goals plausible, tangible, motivational and relevant (though a big reach), at the core of desired transformation with respect to biodiversity and ecosystems. Very relevant and inspirational. Based on previous initiatives (Aichi, SDGs, etc.), not sure if it will be fully implemented.	8	Goal of humans living in harmony w. nature, valuing biodiversity, wise conservation and maintenance of ecosystems will demand significant changes in views and values, along with associated shifts in governance (power structures) and institutions. Very potentially transformative if fully implemented.	7	All three values are present in about equal proportions: instrumental (food, medicine, energy, clean air and waters, ecosystem services), relational (living well in harmony w/ nature), intrinsic—supports all system so life, rights of nature/Mother Earth.	Has been agreed by many nations with potentially powerful transformative impact if fully implemented. Early days at this writing.
2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development 150 40	4	Highly tangible (many specific targets and goals), plausible but a high reach (given lack of progress to date), very inspirational and motivational (having been agreed by nations and signed onto by many businesses), very relevant. I would score higher as it is very relevant an inspirational, although with poor success until now.	6	Wide potential scope for impact along all 17 dimensions of the SDGs. Lack of achievement of targets to date suggests the difficulty of changing necessary views and values, particularly in the dominant mainstream, to encompass these goals, and the consequent need to change power structures and institutions. If achieved, it would be	6-(3-5)	All three values are present, though instrumental values seem to dominate over both relational and intrinsic values.	Yes, there is significant movement on the SDGs, and many attempts to achieve them in a huge array of places, however, current evidence suggests somewhat limited success. Very good intentions, but poor implementation/success until now.

				transformative of most core aspects of societies and human-nature relations. All SDGs seem to be in the same position, meaning that biodiversity/natural capital is not the core of them. To be fully transformative, natural capital should be the core and/or biophysical basis for the economic/social development. See Rockstrom et al. Research shows SDG are indicators of socio-economic development, not necessarily sustainability.			
Everland 106 41	4	Forest specific conservation, transformative investments, with clear goals that are tangible, plausible, and protect biodiversity to benefit all. Somewhat motivational and relevant to the specific contexts, though not easy to achieve.	4	Does not appear to require significant changes in views and values (instrumentality is clear, improving forests to benefit humans), though changes in some institutions (businesses in particular) called for, while there is some recognition of the knowledge of Indigenous peoples, supporting forest communities. Economic, voluntary caron market, and some other indirect drivers marginally present. Conventional tools and actions.	3-6	Highly instrumental orientation, enabling people to prosper from improved forest management. Some recognition of ILK, therefore maybe a bit of relational values expressed.	Appears that there may be some implementation in progress. Not entirely sure.
Commonland 108 42	5	Approach has a high degree of plausibility and tangibility, with specific goals, and a strategic approach that is relevant and potentially motivational while sustaining an economic orientation that will appeal to many existing power holders.	4	Humans in harmony with nature, restoration of landscapes, holistic approach w/ returns for all. Maintains dominant economic logic, therefore does not require much change in views or values, though some power structures and institutions likely need to change at least somewhat to achieve integrated landscape management. Indirect drivers: economic mostly.	3	Highly instrumental, economic orientation, in which nature restoration secures humans' collective future.	Seems like it could be implemented. No specifics on that included.

<p>United Cities and Local Governments 1077</p> <p>43</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Concrete, specific activities developed, collaboration, dialogue, knowledge sharing—advancing community-driven approaches to equity, fairness, sustainability. While tangible and plausible, transformative potential seems limited, therefore less potentially motivational and relevant for local citizens.</p>	<p>3</p> <p>Strategy is not particularly transformative, appearing to operate well within the existing system, with laudable goals that are potentially achievable to some extent on a local scale. Does not seem to require significant views and values, action changes, nor major institutional or power structure reform, hence seemingly limited transformative potential. Voice of local governments, communities. Empowerment of local governments (a world driven by communities). Equity mentioned.</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>Relational: humans living in harmony with nature, ecological/systemic relationship between people and nature.</p>	<p>Network is being implemented, although this may not be very clear from the write-up.</p>
<p>Biophilic Cities Network 1084</p> <p>44</p>	<p>4</p>	<p>Highly tangible and plausible albeit quite limited agenda (understanding of nature's contribution to people in cities). Could be motivational for urban residents and might be able to make relevant w/ the right narrative supporting it. Vision of a 'nature-ful' city is tangible and potentially feasible. Highlighting benefits from biodiversity in cities can be motivational, if only for self-interest.</p>	<p>6</p> <p>Building up understanding of value/contribution of nature to people in cities. Building 'nature-ful' cities. Local views and values impacts are important here, and likely there would be some changes in views, values, actions (promoting nature in cities, for example, though limited in impact overall). Not clear that power structures or institutions would change much. Attention to governance through improved urban-planning is strong. But no attention to other indirect drivers. Equity not mentioned. But engaging cities is quite transformative as they are a powerful actor.</p>	<p>7</p>	<p>Instrumental—benefits of biodiversity and urban wild spaces emphasized, health food options. Relational—conserve nature as shared habitat w/ people and non-humans. Deep personal connection, daily contact with nature, meaningful life, are also clearly relational. Intrinsic—nature stimulates and amazing, 'wonder value' and awe. 'Something larger and outside ourselves'.</p>	<p>Seems like it may be being implemented.</p>

Visions added to fill the gap of intrinsic values in figure 2.5B. These visions are not present in Chapter 2 general vision database

1. Vision name + no. figure 2.5	2. Resistance		3. Comprehensiveness		4. Specific nature value orientation		5. Real world example
	2A	2B	3A	3B	4A	4B	
Ocean rights 45	7	Highly tangible and plausible, grounded in legal rights and ecological understandings. Gives nature a voice to honor cultural connection, support social wellbeing, safeguard ecological integrity. Some nations are not as likely as others to engage in creating such legislation. Based on previous experiences to create new measures/agreements on ocean governance, it is difficult to implement, but if governments can adopt national laws, then the feasibility would be higher.	6	There is a degree of comprehensiveness here, given that assigning rights to Nature for oceans will affect a lot of aspects of societies and where such rights are granted (as has been done in a significant number of places for land or freshwater). The focus is generally on rights and the granting of those rights. Doubts on how people would benefit (equity) from ecosystems and species located beyond the national jurisdictions.	2-4 (but placed in 2)	<p>Intrinsic: Nature for Nature: strongly represented, based in rights, connectivity/primacy of life, reciprocity (fits w/ ILK here), representation and implementation. Values Nature as a living system.</p> <p>Relational values also represented: understanding value, role, interconnectedness of all life on Earth; Nature has spiritual value, cultural heritage, reciprocity, need for humans to stay within cultural limits.</p> <p>Instrumental is mostly downplayed in the interest of intrinsic value.</p>	Wikipedia notes that as of 2021, 39 countries have adopted such measures (for all biomes like rivers), so clearly there are pathways towards making this approach a reality (mostly terrestrial).
Nature Needs Half 46	4	Highly tangible plan to set aside 50% of the Earth's land area as intact natural ecosystems (to save biodiversity) (work w/ energy transition). A bit less plausible than tangible in many contexts that are likely to resist for political (and related) reasons. Ensures networks of protected areas and corridors for biodiversity, mitigate climate change, reduce ecosystem threats. Strongly science-based w/ 5 core goals: 1) represent all native ecosystems, 2) maintain viable species populations, 3) maintain ecosystem	7	Builds on rights of nature movement, argues for securing half of land mass (and some marine) for biodiversity and natural ecosystems. The idea looks simple however the implications are manifold and complex, hence there is a significant degree of multi-dimensionality implied here as many places and institutions and human systems would be affected, and configuration of existing enterprises, governance structures, and the like will all have to change. Some attention to equity issues and indigenous peoples.	2-5 (along the line a bit toward 5, but still in 2 section)	<p>Intrinsic: high intrinsic orientation, focused on saving diversity and abundance of life on earth, avoiding climate change, conserving species, and securing essential ecosystem services (50% of Earth's lands).</p> <p>Instrumental: instrumental values also present to enhance human wellbeing and Indigenous peoples' rights. But much less emphasized than intrinsic.</p> <p>Relational/cultural: mostly not discussed.</p>	Combines three articles, similar to Global Deal for Nature: key areas of implementation are discussed, and possible additional pathways identified.

		function/services; 4) maximize ecosystem carbon sequestration; 5) maintain evolutionary processes and adaptation potential.					
Urban Nature for Nature Future 47	4	Design cities to accommodate natural processes and other-than-humans, compact cities extensive greenspaces. Requires a major shift in worldviews, incorporation of rewilding practices and ecological corridors. There is a high degree of plausibility and feasibility if worldview / mindsets could be shifted as none of the suggestions are implausible—it's a question of designing cities differently. The problem, of course, is the built infrastructure.	7	Encompasses numerous aspects of urban life, design, and associated processes, including placement of buildings, allocation of green spaces and corridors, restoration of natural habitats, cleanup of rivers, recognition of rivers as living systems, shifts in education, housing. Not clear how it deals with indirect drivers, or questions of power. Equity addressed in planning. Speaks about a new (world)view. Addresses structures/institutions.	2 on the axis of 7 where 4 and 5 intersect.	Intrinsic: highly oriented towards nature for nature, however, there is also an instrumental overtone and strong relational qualities are built in.	New paper, no follow up as yet, albeit it is conceivable that some cities could be designed in this way.
Solarpunk Nature for Nature 48	6	As described, significant distance from feasible, though requires significant shifts in the dominant paradigm, changes in land use, wild spaces, human orientation towards non-humans, incorporation of elephants in cities.	6	Very much focused on the incorporation of nature, with not much attention given to other aspects that would need transformation. The city looks quite different than today. There has been a significant change in the dominant worldview towards accepting that nature has not only value in itself but is also higher than humans and shares rights with them. The way the city is managed, the attention of planning to multiple species, indicates an important transformation, including practices and perhaps a bit less, structures. Questions of justice or equity not really addressed, but the notion of co-management implies a re-arrangement of power relations	2	Intrinsic: High expression of intrinsic nature-for-nature values with little else included.	From fiction, not evident in actual places at this time.

				towards more horizontal decisions. Indirect drivers not really addressed.			
Sentient stewards of the sea 49	7	An international treaty granting personhood to nature and limiting access to the high seas have a certain degree of feasibility (see previous visions). The use of technology to monitor and improve the state of the sea, also. But having non-human representatives in governance institutions is highly unfeasible.	6	Reaching this vision would entail a radical change in our worldview, where nature (the sea) is given utmost priority, legal personhood and a role in governance. Indirect drivers: governance and technology, nor questions of power or equity. Considerable change in actions/practices, and to a lesser extent in structures.	2	Vision is strongly centred on intrinsic values.	